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DIGITAL TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCIES REQUIRED BY TEACHERS OF ELECTRICAL/ELECTRONIC TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN NORTH-EAST NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the digital technological competencies required by teachers of electrical/electronic technology education in tertiary institutions in North-East, Nigeria. Four research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. 194 respondents which comprised of 18 heads of ICT unit and 176 electrical/electronic technology education teachers from nine tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria offering Electrical/Electronic Technology Education programme participated in the study. There was no sampling because the population was manageable. The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers and tagged Digital Competencies required by Teachers of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria Questionnaire (DCTTINQ). Three experts validated the instrument and their suggestions were incorporated in the final production of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was further established using Cronbach Alpha method of determining reliability. The reliability index hence stood at 0.88. The four research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 (95%) level of significance. Results from the study revealed that, the digital information competencies which are Storage ($\bar{x} = 4.48$), Search ($\bar{x} = 4.58$), Critical Evaluation ($\bar{x} = 3.89$), and Self-Service ($\bar{x} = 3.90$), as well as digital communication competencies which include Active Participation cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.93$), Collaboration cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.96$), Social Awareness cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), and Media Choice cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.03$) were all required by teachers of electrical/electronic technology education. The results further showed that, there was no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and heads of ICT units in the tertiary institutions. Based on the results and findings of the study therefore, it is recommended that, regular workshops be organized for all teachers in order to improve their abilities in gathering digital information needed to perform their job. Additionally, creation of digital platform and group should be encouraged to enable teachers share ideas and knowledge on digital technologies and communication. This is capable of engendering effective teaching and learning situation especially in electrical/electronic technology education.

Keywords: Digital Technology Competencies, Teachers, Electrical/Electronic Technology

Introduction

The twenty-first century is distinguished by remarkable advances in information and communication technology (ICT). As a result, adjustments in the education system are required to create the needed 21st-century learning environment for 21st-century digital education. Computer and internet technology advancements, in particular, have revolutionized all aspects of human activity over the years. Human interactions are becoming increasingly dependent on technology

improvements as these technologies are integrated into education (Kennedy, Ekong, & Okorie, 2022). It is vital to get instructors to use technology, apply curriculum, and take a 21st-century approach to teaching and learning as expected of 21st-century teachers in handling the educational process of digital natives. Teachers in the twenty-first century are thus required to have a strong knowledge and comprehension of their students' attachment to various technology and what they do with it in their learning process (Haruna, Kabara, & Enriquez, 2022; Vincent, 2022). As a result, human engagement with computers and the internet is rising, and knowledge and abilities in using these technologies are becoming a basic requirement. We live in a linked world in the twenty-first century, where globalization, information and communication technology, and knowledge explosion have shrunk the world into a global village through the digitization of all aspects of education.

Digitalization and technological advancement have fundamentally altered how people think, behave, communicate, and work. In education, the introduction of technology in the twenty-first century has resulted in changes in learning settings and, as a result, the student. The digital transformation has resulted in considerable educational changes, particularly in the development of curricula and instructional methodologies. Technology in the teaching-learning environment allows teachers and students to fit into the worldwide digital age. Teachers in the twenty-first century, according to Raob, Al-Oshaibat, and Lan (2012), demand information to be accessible, instant, and multidimensional. The researchers contend that technology integration in education (digital skills) is one of the 21st Century teacher's competences, particularly the implementation of technology-enhanced classrooms. However, information on how teachers keep up with technological advances is scarce, particularly in underdeveloped nations.

Yildiz (2022) defines digital transformation as opportunities afforded by fast changing Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to provide effective and efficient solutions in domains such as public administration, industry, education, and health. In Electrical Technology Education, for example, technology has become unavoidable for teaching purposes in order to meet the different needs of the present generation and improve their learning environment. The global COVID-19 epidemic has also expanded the use of new technical tools because of the urgent need to convey information, which necessitates the use of virtual platforms and social networks (Manco-Chavez et al., 2020). As a result, in response to the COVID-19 crisis, Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT) introduced alternate methods of teaching with a need for capabilities in generating digital material through ICT, where the crisis has accelerated the digitization of education (Portillo et al., 2020).

Digital competence is a set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes about using technology to perform tasks, solve problems, communicate, manage information, collaborate, and create and share content in an effective, appropriate, secure, critical, creative, independent, and ethical manner. According to the European Commission (2018), digital competence (skills) entails the confident, critical, and responsible use of and interaction with digital technology for learning, work, and societal participation. Falloon (2020) defines digital competence as "the ability to use communication technology tools to access, manage, integrate, evaluate, and create information, as well as the ability to successfully integrate it into everyday life." The concept of digital competence emerged in tandem with technological advancement and as society recognized the need for new skills. Because technological advancement enables and constantly develops new activities and goals, the value of digital competence is constantly evolving and must always be viewed in connection to current technology and its application.

According to Cantabrana, Rodriguez, and Cervera (2019), teachers should integrate digital-age abilities or competencies into their professional activity. Teachers should not just learn fundamental computer applications, but also how to manage information, produce material, and use technology to keep students linked (Portillo et al., 2020). As a result, effective technology integration occurs when students are given the choice to choose technological tools that help them access timely information, analyse and synthesize it, and deliver it professionally (Edutopia, 2017).

Technological knowledge is becoming increasingly crucial since it helps students understand complicated subjects and facilitates peer collaboration (Edutopia, 2017). As a result, teachers in current educational practice are required to employ some type of technology in the classroom. Although practically all categories of people are increasingly using computers, mobile phones, and the internet, this does not necessarily imply that they are developing skills or benefiting from it in a variety of areas. According to research, extensive computer, smart phone, and internet use only contributes to operational digital abilities. Higher cognitive ability for essential information search and selection is not a result of increased consumption. Users can simply remain on the same level and use only certain applications. As a result, high technology use should not be taken as proof of digital competency (Kennedy, Ekong, & Okorie, 2022). However, mastering basic digital tools and internet platforms is only the first step toward mastering advanced digital skills. Digital competence development should be viewed as a progression from instrumental skills to more productive, communicative, critical, and strategic abilities.

Regardless of school level, people need digital skills to engage with the global community, conduct administrative or educational jobs, and be creative/innovative (Osterman, 2012). As a result, technology is crucial in education. Teachers are accountable for integrating technology into the teaching and learning process in order to prepare students for job development in the twenty-first century (Harrell & Bynum, 2018). To produce digitally literate students, instructors must prioritize and employ suitable digital technologies and processes in the classroom (Falloon, 2020). According to Janssen et al. (2013), digital competency entails more than just understanding how to use technology devices and applications. As a result, instructors must be trained with a set of fundamental technological abilities that will be useful when integrating technology into classroom practices.

According to Wedlock and Growe (2017), the most major generational divide has resulted from an explosion of digital technologies, prompting discussions about how to best educate students for the shifting skill set required to be successful in the twenty-first century. The original Bloom Taxonomy and the Revised Bloom Taxonomy are frequently used in education to illustrate instructional cognitive processes that exhibit acceptable learning experiences that result in beneficial academic outcomes for students. Nonetheless, technology-enhanced education is becoming increasingly important in today's classroom change.

When focused on an educational landscape, digital technology presented learners with increased levels of individualization through new ways of interacting in learning (Wetmore, 2017). Learners and teachers have access to software, games, and computer tutors, all of which were designed to aid learning through the use of digital technology. This emphasis on digital technology evolved from theories of cognitive and constructivism presented in the early twentieth century. With the advent of the Internet, students can now access information from websites that allow them to view knowledge from a variety of sources. According to the Queensland Department of Education (2020), this ability to access an infinite amount of material was lauded as a significant development in pedagogy and learning.

By the early 2000s, the Internet had evolved into a dynamic resource that enabled learners to engage in direct contact with others (both speaking and writing) and influence that engagement, such as through content publishing, language translators and zoom meetings. These advancements in digital technology have changed pedagogy and learning by connecting students with the world outside of their classrooms through sophisticated interactions involving knowledge sharing, curating, and production.

Juxtaposed to the introduction of digital technology into schools in the early 21st century was also the rapid technological improvement of computer technology and the concentration on a knowledge society. According to Muianga (2019), the development and availability of newer and more powerful processing systems resulted in new and faster ways of connecting and, as a result, communicating. As a result, these improvements put pressure on schools and instructors to follow suit and discover methods to incorporate technology into their teaching and learning. Digital technology abilities have become highly prized in the society, and this has had a knock-on effect. Tertiary institutions in Nigeria's North-East have limited access to internet services due to a lack of publicly accessible internet. Teachers around the country are finding it challenging to engage in digital teaching and learning due to a lack of dependable technology, internet connectivity, or both. Without appropriate preparation, training, or capacity, a hasty transfer to online teaching and learning may result in a bad experience that impedes long-term growth. To ensure adequate and efficient use of the digital technologies for the purpose of teaching and learning in North East Nigeria, it is necessary to establish the competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st-century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the digital technological competencies required by teachers of electrical/electronic technology education in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria. The study specifically sought to determine the:

1. Digital information competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st-century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria.
2. Digital communication competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st-century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria
3. Digital production competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st-century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria
4. Digital safety competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st-century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the digital information competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria?
2. What are the digital communication competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria?
3. What are the digital production competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria?

4. What are the digital safety competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital information competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital communication competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria.
- H₀₃:** There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital production competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria.
- H₀₄:** There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital safety competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria?

Methodology

The study which was conducted in North East Nigeria adopted a descriptive survey research design. North East, Nigeria is located within latitude 6.26⁰ East and longitude 4.92⁰ North East of the equator. The zone comprises of Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe States. The population of the study was 194 which comprised of 176 Electrical/Electronic Technology Education teachers in tertiary institutions in North-East, Nigeria and 18 ICT unit heads in the nine (9) in tertiary institutions in North-East, Nigeria offering Electrical/Electronic Technology Education. There was no sampling; hence, the whole population was used for the study due to the manageable size of the population. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed by the researchers tagged: “Digital Competencies required by Teachers of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria Questionnaire (DCTTINQ)”. The responses on the questionnaire were structured on a 5-point Rating scale of Very Highly Required (VHR) = 5, Highly Required (HR) = 4, Moderately Required (MR) = 3, Slightly Required (SR) = 2, and Not Required (NR) = 1. The questionnaire was validated by three validates from the Department of Electrical Technology Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Adamawa State. After conducting a trial test of the instrument on five teachers and four ICT unit staff in Federal College of Education (Technical), Bichi in Kano State a reliability index of 0.88 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha method. Data for the study was collected by the researchers with help of five research assistants. Mean statistic was used to answer the four research questions of the study while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses of the study. All items with mean score of 3.50 and above were considered “Required” while all items with less than 3.50 were considered “Not required”. In deciding for the hypothesis, were the p-value was greater than the α -value, the null hypothesis was considered “Significant” and if otherwise “Not Significant”.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the digital information competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Responses on the Digital Information Competencies Required by Teachers in Transforming Electrical/Electronic Technology Education

S/N	Item Statement	Respondents				Remark
		N _T = 176 \bar{x}_T	N _{ICT} = 18 \bar{x}_{ICT}	N = 194 \bar{x}_G	SD	
Digital Information Storage						
1.	The ability to organize digital material	4.01	3.72	3.98	0.29	Required
2.	The ability to store digital material	3.98	3.83	3.97	0.23	Required
3.	The ability to format digital material	4.89	4.44	4.85	0.48	Required
4.	The ability to keep digital material safe	4.90	4.06	4.82	0.80	Required
5.	The ability to keep digital material accessible	4.89	3.89	4.79	0.89	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			4.48		Required
Search						
6.	Ability to search and find digital information	4.94	4.44	4.90	0.44	Required
7.	Ability to navigate between many online resources	4.95	4.50	4.91	0.41	Required
8.	Ability to sort out irrelevant information form digital material	3.97	3.61	3.93	0.34	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			4.58		Required
Critical Evaluation						
9.	Ability to process digital information	3.93	3.83	3.92	0.39	Required
10.	Ability to understand digital information	3.99	3.89	3.98	0.20	Required
11.	Ability to evaluate digital information	3.87	3.72	3.86	0.56	Required
12.	Ability to critique digital information when sent and received	3.84	3.44	3.80	0.67	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			3.89		Required
Self-Service						
13.	Ability to seek-out self-service solutions online	3.86	3.61	3.84	0.65	Required
14.	Ability to determine the benefit from self-service solutions online	3.97	3.72	3.95	0.22	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			3.90		Required

N_T = Number of Teachers, N_{ICT} = Number of Heads of ICT Units, N = Number of Respondents, \bar{x}_T = Mean of Teachers, \bar{x}_{ICT} = Mean of Heads of ICT Units, SD = Standard Deviation, \bar{x}_G = Grand Mean

Table 1 showed the digital information competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria. The responses were grouped into four clusters namely Storage, Search, Critical Evaluation, and Self-Service. From Table 1, the respondents indicated that all the competencies listed in the Storage ($\bar{x} = 4.48$), Search ($\bar{x} = 4.58$), Critical Evaluation ($\bar{x} = 3.89$), and Self-Service ($\bar{x} = 3.90$)

clusters were required by the teachers of electrical/electronic technology education for transformation in the 21st century.

Research Question 2: What are the digital communication competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Responses on the Digital Communication Competencies Required by Teachers in Transforming Electrical/Electronic Technology Education

S/N	Item Statement	Respondents				Remark
		$N_T = 176$ \bar{x}_T	$N_{ICT} = 18$ \bar{x}_{ICT}	$N = 194$ \bar{x}_G	SD	
Communication						
Active Participation						
15.	Ability in making use of digital environments	3.85	3.50	3.81	0.65	Required
16.	Ability in expressing opinions in digital environments	3.90	4.06	3.92	0.53	Required
17.	Ability in contributing actively in digital environments	3.93	4.28	3.96	0.57	Required
18.	Ability in making yourself visible in digital environments	4.01	4.06	4.01	0.10	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			3.93		Required
Collaboration						
19.	Ability to use technologies for teamwork	3.97	3.67	3.94	0.35	Required
20.	Ability to use technologies coordination processes	3.96	3.61	3.93	0.41	Required
21.	Ability to use technologies collaboration processes	4.00	4.00	4.00	0.00	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			3.96		Required
Social Awareness						
22.	Ability to reconcile behavior with regard to context and social relations	3.99	3.94	3.99	0.10	Required
23.	Ability to reconcile tone with regard to context and social relations	3.98	3.83	3.97	0.30	Required
24.	Ability to reconcile language with regard to context and social relations	4.01	4.11	4.02	0.14	Required
25.	Ability to reconcile technology with regard to context and social relations	4.02	4.17	4.03	0.17	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			4.00		Required
Media Choice						
26.	Ability to interact through a wide range of digital platforms	4.04	4.28	4.06	0.24	Required
27.	Ability to choose the best media for communicating with a specific recipient or group	3.98	4.06	3.99	0.31	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			4.03		Required

N_T = Number of Teachers, N_{ICT} = Number of Heads of ICT Units, N = Number of Respondents, \bar{x}_T = Mean of Teachers, \bar{x}_{ICT} = Mean of Heads of ICT Units, SD = Standard Deviation, \bar{x}_G = Grand Mean

Table 2 showed the digital communication competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria. The responses were grouped into four clusters namely Active Participation, Collaboration, Social Awareness, and Media Choice. From Table 1, the respondents indicated that all the competencies listed in the Active Participation cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.93$), Collaboration cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.96$), Social Awareness cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), and Media Choice cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.03$) were required by the teachers of electrical/electronic technology education for transformation in the 21st century.

Research Question 3: What are the digital production competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean Responses on the Digital Production Competencies Required by Teachers in Transforming Electrical/Electronic Technology Education

S/N	Item Statement	N _T = 176 \bar{x}_T	Respondents			Remark
			N _{ICT} = 18 \bar{x}_{ICT}	N = 194 \bar{x}_G	SD	
Production						
Production and Sharing						
28.	Ability to create image content in many different formats	3.97	3.67	3.94	0.43	Required
29.	Ability to create text content in many different formats	4.00	4.00	4.00	0.00	Required
30.	Ability to create video content in many different formats	3.91	3.17	3.85	0.67	Required
31.	Ability to create audio sounds content in many different formats	3.94	3.44	3.90	0.44	Required
32.	Ability to modify content in many different formats	3.96	3.61	3.93	0.41	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			3.92		Required
Digital Exploration						
33.	Ability to stay updated on the technological developments	4.02	4.22	4.04	0.20	Required
34.	Ability to explore new digital opportunities	3.98	3.83	3.97	0.30	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			4.01		Required
Automation						
35.	Ability to modify digital solutions that can fully automate a task	3.95	3.56	3.92	0.40	Required
36.	Ability to create digital solutions that can fully automate a task	4.04	4.22	4.06	0.23	Required
37.	Ability to modify digital solutions that can partially perform a task	3.98	3.83	3.97	0.30	Required
38.	Ability to create digital solutions that can partially perform a task	4.03	4.17	4.05	0.21	Required
	Mean of Grand Mean			4.00		Required

Configuration

39.	Ability to adjust applications and devices to their own personal preferences	4.03	3.94	4.02	0.20	Required
40.	Ability to adjust applications and devices to solve technical problems or tasks	4.04	4.28	4.06	0.24	Required
Mean of Grand Mean				4.04		Required

$N_T =$ Number of Teachers, $N_{ICT} =$ Number of Heads of ICT Units, $N =$ Number of Respondents, $\bar{x}_T =$ Mean of Teachers, $\bar{x}_{ICT} =$ Mean of Heads of ICT Units, $SD =$ Standard Deviation, $\bar{x}_G =$ Grand Mean

Table 3 showed the digital production competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria. The responses were grouped into four clusters namely Active Participation, Collaboration, Social Awareness, and Media Choice. From Table 1, the respondents indicated that all the competencies listed in the Production and Sharing cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.92$), Digital Exploration cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.01$), Automation cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), and Configuration cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.04$) were required by the teachers of electrical/electronic technology education for transformation in the 21st century.

Research Question 4: What are the digital safety competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria?

Table 4: Mean Responses on the Digital Safety Competencies Required by Teachers in Transforming Electrical/Electronic Technology Education

S/N	Item Statement	Respondents				Remark
		$N_T = 176$ \bar{x}_T	$N_{ICT} = 18$ \bar{x}_{ICT}	$N = 194$ \bar{x}_G	SD	
Safety						
Law						
41.	The ability to identify current laws for digital information and content	4.02	4.22	4.04	0.20	Required
42.	The ability to identify current licenses for digital behavior	3.98	3.78	3.96	0.20	Required
43.	The ability to identify prescribed digital behavior	4.02	4.17	4.03	0.17	Required
Mean of Grand Mean				4.01		Required
Identity Management						
44.	Ability to monitor your personal information online	3.99	3.94	3.99	0.23	Required
45.	Ability to protect your personal information online	3.99	3.94	3.99	0.18	Required
46.	Ability to understand the consequences of personal digital footprints	3.99	3.89	3.98	0.14	Required
Mean of Grand Mean				3.99		Required

Data Protection						
47.	Ability to identify sensitive data	3.99	3.72	3.97	0.27	Required
48.	Ability to protect sensitive data	3.97	3.94	3.97	0.17	Required
49.	Ability to understand related risks of data safety	4.05	3.72	4.02	0.26	Required
Mean of Grand Mean				3.99		Required
Health						
50.	Ability to care for physical health in everyday life surrounded by technology	4.02	4.17	4.03	0.23	Required
51.	Ability to care for mental health in everyday life surrounded by technology	3.98	3.78	3.96	0.20	Required
52.	Ability to identify dangerous applications on the system	3.99	3.94	3.99	0.34	Required
Mean of Grand Mean				3.99		Required

N_T = Number of Teachers, N_{ICT} = Number of Heads of ICT Units, N = Number of Respondents, \bar{x}_T = Mean of Teachers, \bar{x}_{ICT} = Mean of Heads of ICT Units, SD = Standard Deviation, \bar{x}_G = Grand Mean

Table 4 showed the digital safety competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria. The responses were grouped into four clusters namely Active Participation, Collaboration, Social Awareness, and Media Choice. From Table 1, the respondents indicated that all the competencies listed in the Law cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.01$), Identity Management cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.99$), Data Protection cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.99$), and Health cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.99$) were required by the teachers of electrical/electronic technology education for transformation in the 21st century.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital information competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria.

Table 5: t-test on the Digital Information Competencies Required by Teachers in Transforming Electrical/Electronic Technology Education in the 21st Century

Respondents	N	Mean	SD	df	P – value	Remark
Teachers	176	4.28	0.30	192	0.12	Not Significant
Heads of ICTs	18	3.91	0.75			

$P > 0.05$ N= Number of respondents, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 5 is the result obtained when the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The p-value stood at 0.12. Since the p-value is greater than the α -value of 0.05, implies that the null hypothesis is therefore upheld.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of Teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital communication competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria.

Table 6: t-test on the Digital Communication Competencies Required by Teachers in Transforming Electrical/Electronic Technology Education in the 21st Century

Respondents	N	Mean	SD	df	P – value	Remark
Teachers	176	3.97	0.14	192	0.86	Not Significant
Heads of ICTs	18	3.97	0.15			

P > 0.05 N= Number of respondents, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 6 is the result obtained when the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The p-value stood at 0.86. Since the p-value is greater than the α -value of 0.05, implies that the null hypothesis is therefore upheld.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital production competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria.

Table 7: t-test on the Digital Production Competencies Required by Teachers in Transforming Electrical/Electronic Technology Education in the 21st Century

Respondents	N	Mean	SD	df	P – value	Remark
Teachers	176	3.99	0.11	192	0.62	Not Significant
Heads of ICTs	18	3.84	0.30			

P > 0.05 N= Number of respondents, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 7 is the result obtained when the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The p-value stood at 0.62. Since the p-value is greater than the α -value of 0.05, implies that the null hypothesis is therefore upheld.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital safety competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria.

Table 8: t-test on the Digital Safety Competencies Required by Teachers in Transforming Electrical/Electronic Technology Education in the 21st Century

Respondents	N	Mean	SD	df	P – value	Remark
Teachers	176	4.00	0.05	192	0.17	Not Significant
Heads of ICTs	18	3.94	0.19			

P > 0.05 N= Number of respondents, SD = Standard Deviation

Table 8 is the result obtained when the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The p-value stood at 0.17. Since the p-value is greater than the α -value of 0.05, implies that the null hypothesis is therefore upheld.

Discussions

The findings of the study revealed that in digital information competencies, the competencies in Storage (\bar{x} = 4.48), Search (\bar{x} = 4.58), Critical Evaluation (\bar{x} = 3.89), and Self-Service (\bar{x} = 3.90) clusters were required by the teachers of electrical/electronic technology education for transformation in the 21st century. The supporting hypothesis revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital information competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria. The findings is in agreement with Igbinovia, Okuonghae and Adebayo (2021) and Usman and Madudili (2020) who reported that there abound digital information in the internet but one needs a specific

skill to enable him/her to be able search for the correct information and where to get one. In further support of the findings, Oguguo et al. (2020) reported that critical evaluation of the information obtained from the internet needs to be scrutinized and sorted in order to make the information relevant.

The findings of the study revealed that in digital communication competencies, the competencies in Active Participation cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.93$), Collaboration cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.96$), Social Awareness cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), and Media Choice cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.03$) were required by the teachers of electrical/electronic technology education for transformation in the 21st century. The complimenting hypothesis revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital communication competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria. The findings is in agreement with Chukwuedo and Ogbuanya (2020) and Bakare et al. (2020) reported that communication has gone beyond human and human to human and machines. The teachers have to ensure that the medium of communication is not bridged in order for communication to flow and the messages embedded well understood. Rodzalan et al. (2022) noted that in digital communication, collaboration and social awareness is of essence and as such communicators must ensure adequate flow of information.

The findings of the study revealed that in digital production competencies, the competencies in Production and Sharing cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.92$), Digital Exploration cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.01$), Automation cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), and Configuration cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.04$) were required by the teachers of electrical/electronic technology education for transformation in the 21st century. The accompanying hypothesis revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital production competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria. The findings is in agreement with Matthew and Kazaure (2020), Elekwachi and Mekuri-Ndimele (2022) and Elekwachi and Mekuri-Ndimele (2022) in their separate submissions reported that technical teachers have to be creative, innovative and explorers. The authors emphasizes that only teachers that are creative and innovative can be productive as the need to digitally produce learning content which will be in line with the curriculum as well as the learners maturity and abilities. In line with the findings, Ayinde and Kirkwood reported that (2020) ICT is basically concerned with the production and use of digital information as such a teacher should possess the skills which will enable him/her to produce learning materials and use it for the betterment of the student's academic achievement.

The findings of the study revealed that in safety competencies, the competencies in Law cluster ($\bar{x} = 4.01$), Identity Management cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.99$), Data Protection cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.99$), and Health cluster ($\bar{x} = 3.99$) were required by the teachers of electrical/electronic technology education for transformation in the 21st century. The supporting hypothesis revealed that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and Heads of ICT Unit on the digital safety competencies required by teachers in transforming electrical/electronic technology education in the 21st century in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria. The findings is in agreement with Owo and Deebom (2020), Ayinde and Kirkwood (2020), Bakare et al. (2020), Oguguo et al. (2020) noted that the knowledge of the rules and regulations governing the use of any digital application must be well understood before the user uses the application. For this, call by the authors highlighted that all users must ensure that they understand the terms and conditions attached to every application and service provided online. They must also have adequate knowledge on how to patent their productions as well as protect their data. Usman and Madudili (2020) asserted that safety in terms of personal health is of great paramount as most digital

gadget comes with devastating health issues that will affect the well-being of the users.

Conclusion

The study concluded that in the 21st century, teachers in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria required digital technological competencies in digital information, digital communication, digital production, and digital safety in order to transform electrical/electronic technology education.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of the study, the following were recommended:

1. Regular workshop should be organized by the Department of Electrical/Electronic Technology Education in tertiary institutions in North-East Nigeria for all teachers in order to improve their abilities in gathering digital information needed.
2. Teacher should form a group in which they can share ideas and knowledge on digital communication widespread used in teaching and learning situations especially in electrical/electronic technology education.
3. Teacher should be guided on how to produce digital materials needed for the effective teaching and learning of electrical/electronic technology education
4. Law and safety officers should be invited to enlighten the teachers on the need to understand the rules and regulations governing the use of any digital platform and as well understand the risks associated with each digital gadgets.

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